

CHAIN EXTENSION REACTION OF PA1010 BY 2,2'-BIS(2-OXAZOLINE)

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ABSTRACT: The reaction behavior of 2,2'-bis(2-oxazoline) (BOZ) has been studied to evaluate its coupling effects as the chain extender for polyamide1010 (PA1010). It has been observed that the torque of PA1010 melt increased dramatically with the increase of reaction time. The maximal torque of PA1010 melt also increased with increasing the content of BOZ. However, addition of excess amount of BOZ led to more blocking reaction, not coupling reaction, indicating that the PA1010 of not-so-much-increased molecular weight but much-decreased carboxyl concentration would be produced. The PA1010, with end carboxyl group concentration of $52.8 \text{ eq}/10^6 \text{ g}$ and melt torque of 0.7 Nm at 240°C with a rotor speed of 40rpm, was added 0.84wt% BOZ to carry out a chain extension reaction. The resultant PA1010 having end carboxyl concentration of $8.2 \text{ eq}/10^6 \text{ g}$ and melt torque of 3.3 Nm was achieved, after an optimal reaction time. The effect of temperature on the chain extension reaction rate accords with the Arrhenius exponential formula. In addition to temperature, the shear rate also has some effects on the chain-extension rate, which indicated that the higher the shear rate, the higher the reaction rate.

KEYWORDS: PA 1010; Chain extension; Bisoxazoline. degradation; Kinetic.

1- Introduction

Polyamide1010 (PA1010) is a well-known commercial plastic with numerous applications, such as fiber, automobile parts, and engineering components. Due to its high crystallinity, PA has a great deal of advantages such as high strength, self-oiling, resistance to chemicals, oils and abrasion. It has been produced by polycondensing a mixture of diamine and dicarboxyl in the presence of catalysts at a high temperature and in a vacuum[1]. However, the common grades of PA1010 with a relatively low molecular weight have inferior mechanical properties and can not meet the requirements of some applications. The standard industrial polymerization processes are efficient only in producing PA with a limited M_w because the high viscosity makes it very difficult for small molecules, such as water, to escape. To overcome the limitation, a post-polycondensation method in solid phase has been developed, however, the very slow reaction rate and the necessity of large special equipments limit its application. For this reason, the chain extension is an attractive option. The chain extenders for PA are generally bifunctional compounds that can react easily with the end groups of PA and link two or more polymer chains together, producing PA with relatively high molecular weight[2].

Chemicals that can be used as concentrate-type chain extenders such as phosphate ester, phosphite ester, could generate some high boiling-point by-products in chain extension reaction, though they do have some effects on chain extension. An example is shown in Scheme 1. Consequently, addition-type chain extenders generating no by-products are

preferable. Bifunctional compounds, such as diepoxides, diisocyanates, and bis(cyclic carboxylic anhydride), belong to this kind[3-5]. However, some of these bifunctional chain extenders, may cause undesirable branching, crosslinking or introduce less thermally stable linkages in the main chain of PA with immoderate content.

Inata and Matsumura used many types of oxazines, such as bicyclic-imino-ethers, as chain extenders for both PBT and PET[6-11]. Both those reacting with carboxyl groups and those reacting with hydroxyl groups can help the chain extension of polyesters[12-14]. The reaction with the carboxyl group and the hydroxyl group are shown in Scheme 2. Other researchers have also used various kinds of chain extenders for polyesters, most of which stand a good chance to help increase the molecular weight of polyamides.

Chatamet and Taha prepared a bisoxazoline coupling agent (1,3-phenylene)-bisoxazoline, by which the kinetic and rheokinetic research were studied[15,16]. The kinetic study, basing on the ideal linear model, showed a similar reactivity of the two oxazoline rings, and the rheokinetic study revealed that the reactive system showed Newtonian behavior at relatively low shear rates. Dicarboxylic fatty acid or carboxyl terminated oligoamide was chosen as the model reactant to avoid the high-viscosity diffusibility and the non-Newton behavior.

The study aims to lay out the coupling effects of bisoxazolines and the thermal stability of the chain-extended products. The optimal content of chain extender was obtained at different reaction temperatures. The results indicated that 2,2'-bis(2-oxazoline) was an effective chain extender without engendering any gel for PA1010. After the melt torque reached its peak value, slow degradation was detected, which showed that there existed an optimal reaction time for chain extension.

On the other hand, we propose a model to study the influence of reaction conditions, such as temperature and chain extender dosage by simulating the value of k and r , and modified the ideal linear model. The existence of optimal dosage of chain extender, the degradation phenomenon and the distinction of BOZ and PBO, can be easily explained by the modified model, though it cannot be analysed in a quantitative way due to the diffusibility and the non-Newton behavior of polymer melt.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

2- Experimental

2.1- Materials

Polyamide1010 was supplied by Tianjin Zhonghe Chemical Factory, China. BOZ was purchased from TCI(Tokyo Chemical Industry Co., Ltd.) Starting materials were used as received without any purification except drying at 80°C for 12h.

2.2- Chain extension reaction

Some well-dried PA pellets were added into the mixing chamber of a Haake rheometer. The rotor speed varied from 40 to 100 rpm, but normally 40rpm, and the temperature rised from

220 to 280°C. After complete melting of the pellets, chain extender BOZ was added into the PA melt. The melt torque during mixing, was used to measure the extent of the reaction. Reaction time was prolonged to evaluate the thermal stability of the chain-extended products.

2.3- Characterization of the products

Carboxyl contents were determined by the Waltz-Taylor method. The sample was dissolved in 50ml preheated benzyl alcohol. Titration of the solution was performed using a microtitrator whose scale is 0.02ml with KOH/ethanol solution. A blank titration was performed on 50ml of pure benzyl alcohol under the same conditions.

Concentration of amine end group was determined by Elias method. The sample was dissolved in 30ml of m-cresol. Titration of this solution was performed using a microtitrator whose scale is 0.02ml with hydrochloric acid solution.

3- Results and discussion

The reactions of BOZ with the PA1010 end groups have been summarized in Scheme 5. And its reactivity with end carboxyl groups is much higher than that with end amino groups at high temperature, therefore the latter reaction can be neglected in this reaction system.

3.1- Effect of chain extension

Changes of the relative torque of polyamide melt with different amount of BOZ was recorded by Haake mixer and presented in Figure 1 and Figure2, where the reaction temperatures are respectively 240°C and 260 °C. The ratio of the torque during the reaction process and the original torque was regarded as the relative torque for polyamide melt, because this can help standardize the effect of chain extension at different temperatures. The experimental curves were smoothed by mathematical software Origin.

A conclusion can be drawn from Figure 1 and Figure 2 that relative torque reached its maximum when definite amount of BOZ was used. Excess amount of chain extender can cause decrease of chain extension effect. So there exist an optimal value of BOZ amount, by which the polyamide melt torque increased more than 4 times as origin. It was also shown that the optimal amount of BOZ may be different at various reaction temperatures, which is approximately 0.84(wt)% in the first figure, but 1.21(wt)% in the second figure, as together presented in Figure 3.

Different amounts of chain extender BOZ were added to PA1010, with end carboxyl group concentration of 52.8 eq/10⁶g. The Results demonstrated that the carboxyl group content decreased dramatically with the increase of BOZ, and showed an unchanged trend at the end of the curve, as presented in Figure 4. There remained a small quality of carboxyl group finally, and higher temperature gave less carboxyl group. Furthermore, the amino groups kept approximately constant during the process, except that oxidation at high temperature led to some extent to its decrease at the beginning.

3.2-Effect of temperature and Shear rate on Chain extension

An Arrhenius type plot showing the relationship between reaction time and temperature is shown in Figure 5. The time when the torque reached the maximum value was regarded as the time for the completion of the reaction. The time required for the completion of the reaction decreased dramatically with increasing reaction temperature. The chain-extension reaction was completed in 3 minutes at a rotor speed of 40rpm when the reaction temperature was

above 280°C. In addition to the temperature, the shear rate also has some effect on the chain-extension rate, as shown in Figure 6. An increase in the shear rate increases the diffusion rate of BOZ in the PA melt; hence, the chain-extension reaction rate increases. However, too much higher rotor speed may not do good to the chain-extension reaction so that an appropriate rotor speed is desired. A very small amount of residual BOZ, which does not produce any side effects on the chain-extended product, can act as a stabilizer to compensate for the hydrolyzation during further processing.

Figure 1- Torque changes with PA1010 with time by BOZ(240°C)

Figure 2- Torque changes with PA1010 with time by BOZ(260°C)

Figure 3- Maximum torque changes with content of BOZ

Figure 4- Carboxyl content changes with content of BOZ

Nevertheless, the fact of “degradation” of the chain-extended product was discovered when high reaction temperature was kept for a very long time, such as 2 hours. The decrease of melt torque was obviously recorded by Haake mixer, as shown in Figure 7. It meant that there should exist some unstable chemical bond in the chain-extended product. Another experiment was designed to study whether there is any degradation of virgin PA1010 or not. We found with curiosity that the melt torque of virgin PA1010 in the Haake mixer did not decrease, but increase slightly with time. This showed at least a fact that the “degradation” of the chain-extension product must occur at new site created by BOZ. Further research indicated that the unstable part of the product is probably oxalic group. Hence, heating process does not always increase the properties of the chain-extension product, and it depends on the conversion of the reaction. It should be adjusted corresponding to different technical process.

Figure 5- Reaction time changes with temperature

Figure 6- Reaction time changes with rotor speed

Figure 7- Degradation of chain extension product

Figure 8- Torque changes of virgin PA1010 with time

3.3- Theoretical analysis of chain extension

In chain-extension reactions by bisoxazolines, reaction behavior of carboxyl terminals contained in the initial polymers can be classified into three groups: “blocked”, “coupled” and “unreacted”, as shown in Scheme 3. As can be easily understood, theoretically, the chain extender should be added in an equimolar amount to the carboxyl terminals in the initial polymer to result in the highest-molecular-weight polymer after the chain-extension reaction. If an excess amount of the chain extender should be added, the blocking reaction would occur predominantly and the polymer of not-so-much-increased molecular weight but much-decreased carboxyl content should result. The variation of carboxyl terminals involved in different kinds of reaction was simulated in Figure 9, which illustrates that the ratio of blocked carboxyl groups and coupled carboxyl groups goes on increasing with adding the amount of chain extender. Therefore, not only does using excess chain extenders waste highly efficient additive, but also leads to less chain extension effect.

Scheme 3- Different reactions of bisoxazoline with carboxyl

The theoretical amount of the chain extender to be added can be calculated as follows:

$$Q_r = 1/2 * CC_0 * M_{BOZ}$$

Where M_{BOZ} is the molecular weight of the chain extender and CC_0 is carboxyl content of the initial PA1010.

As can be observed in Figure 3 and 4, relative torque reached its maximum when approximately 1.9 times as much as theoretical amount of BOZ was used. This deviation was probably due to the loss of the chain extender during the reaction by sublimation or decomposition.

Coupling efficiency can be evaluated as follows:

Defining:

$$N_C \sim [\text{COOH}], \text{ mol/g}, N_A \sim [\text{NH}_2], \text{ mol/g}$$

$$CE \sim p, R = N_C / N_A$$

Weight average Molar mass

	M	→	2M
originally	$2R/(1+R)$		0
finally	$(1-p) * 2R/(1+R)$		$pR/(1+R)$

$$M_{w,t}/M_{w,0} = \frac{\sum N_i M_i^2}{\sum N_i M_i} / M_{w,0}$$

$$= [1 + 2Rp/(1+R)]$$

$$= 1 + 2Rp/(1+R)$$

It can be draw a conclusion from above that the value of R and p is the key factor of chain extension reactions. What we should pay much attention to is how to increase the value of them by practical methods.

Figure 9- Simulation of different forms of carboxyl reaction

4-Conclusion

From the above results, the following conclusions can be drawn.

1. 2,2'-bis(2-oxazoline) used in this study is an effective chain extender for PA1010.

2. The time needed for this chain-extension reaction can be less than 3 min; so it can be performed in a twin-screw-extruder.
3. The best effect of chain extension should be controlled by optimal amount of chain extender and moderate reaction conditions such as temperature, rotor speed and reaction time.

5-Acknowledgements

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